

**Studies on Oxidation of Cyclohexene using
CrO₃/70% tert-Butyl Hydroperoxide
(TBHP) System**

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THE catalytic functionalisation of various types of hydrocarbons with such terminal oxidants as dioxygen, peroxides, non-metal oxides etc. are of both chemical and biochemical importance^{1,2}. Among such transformations, the metal catalysed conversion of an olefin to its epoxide by oxygen transfer poses an intriguing synthetic and theoretical challenge. Various catalytic systems have been tried³ but the mechanism is still not clear and in most cases the yields are low. In continuation of our recent interest in evaluating various catalytic systems⁴⁻⁷, we have studied a simple system using commercially available CrO₃ and 70% tert-butyl hydroperoxide. We have found that cyclohexene undergoes epoxidation with this reagent system. This system is also capable of hydroxylating cyclohexane. The effect of additives, competitive epoxidation of cyclo-olefins have been studied and a suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Experimental

Cyclohexene, cyclohexane, cycloheptene, norbornene, 70% tert-butyl hydroperoxide (Aldrich) were used. Cyclohexene was purified⁸ and stored at -20°. All the standard samples of epoxide and cyclohexenol were prepared as reported earlier^{4,5}. NaHCO₃, NaH₂PO₄, pyridine, Triton X-100, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTABr) and sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) were obtained from Aldrich, Glaxo and Loba. Benzene, dichloromethane, acetonitrile and acetone used as solvent were purified⁸. A Nucon-Amil 5700 gas chromatograph fitted with a Shimadzu C-R-3A data processor was used for product analysis.

Procedure for catalytic epoxidation: In a typical procedure, cyclohexene (8 mmol) in benzene (5 ml) was treated with CrO₃ (0.001 mmol) and 70% TBHP (8 mmol) at 80° for 3 h with continuous stirring under N₂-atmosphere. After the reaction was over, the contents were worked up by adding sodium sulphite to destroy unreacted tert-butyl hydroperoxide and then extracting with ether, followed by drying with anhydrous MgSO₄. The samples were analysed by gas chromatography using a XE-60 column at 120°.

The effect of solvents CH₂Cl₂, CH₃CN and acetone using the same composition and conditions as stated above was studied. For CrO₃/30% H₂O₂ system, the contents were taken as follows: CrO₃ (0.001 mmol), cyclohexene (8 mmol), 30% H₂O₂

TABLE 1—EPOXIDATION OF CYCLOHEXENE USING VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Sl. no.	Solvent	Epoxide %	Peroxide %	Cyclohexenol %	Cyclohexenone %	Catalyst turnover no.
1.	CH ₃ CH	0.03	Traces	8.2	2.3	2.0
2.	C ₆ H ₆	12.3	7.5	2.6	2.0	980.0
3.	CH ₂ Cl ₂	11.2	32.5	19.5	7.1	900.0
4.	CH ₃ COCH ₃	0.06	Nil	7.8	2.4	5.0

(8 mmol) and solvent (5 ml), viz. CH₃CN, CH₂Cl₂ or acetone.

Effect of additives: The effect of additives on the epoxidation of cyclohexene in CrO₃/70% TBHP system was studied. A mixture of CrO₃ (0.001 mmol), 70% TBHP (8 mmol), cyclohexene (8 mmol) and benzene (5 ml) as solvent was heated at 80° with the additive (100 mg) in each experiment.

Competitive epoxidation of cyclo-olefins: The competitive epoxidation was studied taking cyclohexene (8 mmol) and other cyclic olefin (8 mmol) together in benzene (5 ml) along with CrO₃ (0.001 mmol) and 70% tert-butylhydroperoxide (8 mmol) at 80° for 3 h.

Oxidation of cyclohexane: CrO₃ (0.001 mmol), cyclohexane (8 mmol), 70% TBHP (24 mmol) and solvent CH₃CN, benzene or acetone (5 ml) were used in each reaction. The contents were heated for 2 h at 80°. The effect of 70% TBHP concentration on oxidation of cyclohexane was also studied by taking 8, 16 and 24 mmol of 70% TBHP.

Results and Discussion

The epoxidation of cyclohexene using CrO₃/70% TBHP system in various solvent systems, viz. benzene, dichloromethane, acetonitrile and acetone showed the formation of four major products (Table 1) cyclohexene oxide, cyclohexenyl peroxide, cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone. In benzene solvent, the epoxide formation was favoured compared to peroxide, cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone. In CH₂Cl₂, the yield of epoxide was comparable to that in benzene but peroxide and cyclohexenol were formed in large amounts. Acetone and acetonitrile solvents do not induce considerable epoxidation of cyclohexene. So benzene was the better choice as solvent for the above system. The results show that the medium of epoxidation has an effect on the selectivity of epoxide. The reaction of CrO₃ with cyclohexene in absence of 70% TBHP did not give any product. The reaction did not take place between cyclohexene and 70% TBHP in the absence of CrO₃. These results with CrO₃/70% TBHP system are in contrast to that observed with O=Mo (TPP) OMe/TBHP⁹ and O=Ti (TPP)/TBHP¹⁰ systems where only dry TBHP acted as oxidant while 70% TBHP gave no reaction.

The effect of additives, viz. pyridine, NaH₂PO₄ and NaHCO₃ on the epoxidation of cyclohexene

shows a negative effects on the yield of epoxide (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ADDITIVES ON EPOXIDATION OF CYCLOHEXENE

Sl. no.	Additive	Epoxide %	Peroxide %	Cyclohexenol %	Cyclohexenone %
1.	Cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide	0.5	42.7	Traces	1.5
2.	Triton X-100	0.3	8.1	2.5	Traces
3.	Sodium lauryl sulphate	0.1	7.3	0.03	Traces
4.	NaH ₂ PO ₄	3.3	Traces	2.3	0.7
5.	NaHCO ₃	0.8	Nil	5.8	5.3
6.	Pyridine	1.8	12.6	0.8	0.5

The presence of each of surfactants sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), Triton X-100 and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTABr) decreases the yield of all the products. It means that anionic/non-ionic and cationic species decrease epoxidation. NaH₂PO₄ and NaHCO₃ both reduce the yield of epoxide and peroxide but the yield of allylic oxidation was high in the presence of NaHCO₃. The addition of pyridine reduced the yield of epoxide but the yields of cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone were also insignificant. This shows that pyridine inhibits the formation of allylic oxidation products too.

The competitive epoxidation of cyclo-olefins follows the reactivity order: norbornene (5.8) > cycloheptene (4.0) > cyclohexene (1.0), showing that coordination of the olefins to the metal center is not the rate-determining step. Had olefin coordinated to the metal center in the rate-determining step, then the cyclohexene would have reacted faster than cycloheptene and norbornene. It may be assumed that torsional and bond angle strain might have some significant role in determining the relative reactivity of cyclo-olefins^{2,6}.

Epoxidation of cyclohexene using 30% H₂O₂ as oxidant in acetonitrile and dichloromethane solvent gave no product. In acetone solvent, epoxide was formed in traces but cyclohexenol (3.98%) and cyclohexenone (2.1%) were formed. This shows that hydrogen peroxide is a poor oxidant compared to tert-butylhydroperoxide.

As CrO₃ gave high yields of cyclohexenol and cyclohexenone, it was thought interesting to study alkane (cyclohexane) activation using 70% TBHP.

It was observed that the yield of cyclohexanol from cyclohexane using solvent acetonitrile, benzene, dichloromethane and acetone was 0.99, 0.06, nil and 0.83% respectively. The effect of TBHP concentration shows that maximum yield (0.99%) was observed at 24 mmol of TBHP. At 8 and 16 mmol concentrations of TBHP, 0.04 and 0.43% respectively of cyclohexanol were observed. CrO₃ adsorbed over silica gel shows that cyclohexanol formation was increased 36-times showing that silica gel acts as a positive support.

Mechanism: It was observed that CrO₃ reacts with 70% TBHP resulting in the development of deep orange-red colour which can be attributed to a peroxo-metal intermediate¹¹ (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The formation of peroxide and allylic oxidation product shows that homolytic decomposition of tert-butyl hydroperoxide is the important pathway for the catalytic oxidation. The formation of allylic oxidation products has been reported by Groves *et al.*^{1,2} in Cr^{III}(TPP)Cl/PhIO system.

It can be concluded that commercial tert-butyl hydroperoxide can be used conveniently for the oxidation of cyclohexene and cyclohexane.

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